

CityMove

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03

DEC Programming 2025

D6.1: DEC Strategy

Author: Walk21

Funded by
the European Union

DEC programming 2025

As a follow-up to the communication strategy of the CityMove project (DEC strategy), this operational plan is designed to programme the communication activities for the 12-month period January-December 2025. It is based on the complete project and its strategic objectives, as well as the lines of communication, dissemination and exploitation outlined in the DEC strategy.

The objectives of the DEC strategy to be taken forward are:

1. Effectively showcase and amplify the activities and outcomes of the project at the international, regional, and local levels.
2. Promote the data and findings from the evaluation of 13 PA interventions ensuring that these findings are accessible and understandable to a diverse range of stakeholders.
3. Position CITY-MOVE as a notable contribution in the field of PA while raising awareness, showcasing the results of the project, and promoting the replication of the City-GAPPA interventions.

The messages to be promoted are those contained in the DEC strategy:

- Cities are a potential enabler of change to increase PA.
- CITY-MOVE offers a unique exploration and evaluation of 13 city-GAPPA interventions across diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts (6 cities and 3 continents).
- CITY-MOVE is a valuable knowledge hub for the successful implementation of adaptable PA interventions (based on the GAPPA).
- CITY-MOVE accelerates and supports action for PA.

The project's core communication actions in 2025, according to the DEC, will revolve around:

- **M6.1.** Skills and training audit performed (Q2, 2024)
- **M1.3.** Core context elements identified (Q1, 2025)
- **D1.1. CITY-MOVE ToC.** Report of the initial CITY-MOVE ToC (Q2, 2025)
- **M2.1.** First co-production session held in each city (Q2, 2025)
- **M5.1.** Defining the decision problem (Q2, 2025)
- **M6.2.** First meeting of each regional CoP (Q2, 2025)
- **M7.3.** CCAB established (Q2, 2025)
- **D5.1. MDCA core set.** A core process, cost (-effectiveness) and outcome indicator set for MCDA (Q4, 2025)

These activities are carried out by teams from all cities, so their development within the framework of the DEC depends entirely on the development of the project actions.

The CityMove Communication Programming 2025 has the objective to strengthen visibility and engagement through strategic communication activities, leveraging GAPPA's framework, EU platforms, and city-level initiatives to promote the project's research, interventions, and outcomes.

Strategic Focus for 2025

The communication programming for 2025 will align closely with the project's milestones and deliverables, ensuring that all key activities are effectively disseminated and stakeholders remain informed and engaged. The plan will prioritise creating awareness around CityMove's Theory of Change (ToC), co-production sessions, regional Communities of Practice (CoPs), and the Multi-Criteria Decision Assessment (MCDA) outcomes.

Each activity includes actions, timeline, channels, objectives, and intended impact, ensuring alignment with CityMove's goals. Below are the guidelines for the communication content to be carried out in 2025:

1. City-Specific Communication Activities				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>Updates from Bogotá, Lima, Kampala, Antwerp, Rotterdam, and Ljubljana highlighting intervention progress, milestones, and events.</p> <p>Objective: Strengthen awareness of city-specific interventions, fostering engagement with local stakeholders.</p> <p>Impact: Promote visibility of local actions, empowering city teams to connect with residents and stakeholders.</p>	<p>Format: Localised communication materials aligned with CityMove branding guidelines. (Photo or video)</p> <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CityMove website and official newsletters. • Local and global social media platforms. 	<p>Bimonthly updates submitted by the last week of each quarter:</p> <p>Dates and cities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible, according to updates. 		6 update posts (one for each city)
2. Blogs and news				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>Develop blogs highlighting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Late interventions in H1 2025 • Early interventions in H2 2025 <p>Objective: Create a comprehensive record of intervention progress and achievements while showcasing individual city efforts.</p> <p>Impact: Enhance visibility of CityMove's milestones, fostering engagement and providing a lasting knowledge resource.</p>	<p>Format: A blog post for each of the 13 interventions, focusing on stories about those interventions (or how they were created, or impact figures, or user testimonials). Every city contributes key data and</p>	<p>One blog per month, starting with late interventions and secondly with early interventions.</p> <p>Dates and cities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • March28: <u>Antwerp</u>, "Exercise on Prescription" and "Health Kiosk, Terloplein" 		12 blogs, one for each of the 12 interventions (the blog for the 13 intervention, the Bogotá Ciclovía, was published in December 2024)

	<p>collaborates for storytelling.</p> <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CityMove website. • CityMove social media. • CityMove global Newsletter. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • April28: <u>Kampala</u>, “NMT Pilot Corridor” • May25: <u>Lima</u>, “Pan American Games Legacy” • June30: <u>Ljubljana</u>, “Walk Along the Wire” • July 27: <u>Rotterdam</u>, “Green Walking Routes” • August25: <u>Antwerp</u>, “Brave-Move” • September29: <u>Bogotá</u>, “Happiness Centres” • September 26: <u>Kampala</u>, “Kampala Car-Free Day” • October 24: <u>Lima</u>, “Independencia Greenbelt” • November 28: <u>Ljubljana</u>, “Walking Gaming App” • December 11: <u>Rotterdam</u>, “Green Connection” 		
3. Newsletters				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>Produce:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One general newsletter (biannual) summarising key project achievements. • Regional newsletter: with information on the interventions in each city by region (Latin America, Europe and Africa) on H2. <p>Objective: Provide consistent project updates to stakeholders, promoting transparency and collaboration.</p> <p>Impact: Strengthen engagement with stakeholders while amplifying CityMove’s key messages.</p>	<p>Format:</p> <p>Bulletin-style newsletter with the template developed in 2024 for sending via Mailchimp.</p> <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CityMove’s email distribution. • Partner networks 	<p>Flexible dates</p> <p>General newsletters in June and December:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • July 10 • December 16 <p>Flexible dates for partner inputs aligned with their schedules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europe, • Africa, • Latinamerica 		<p>2 Global Newsletters</p> <p>3 Regional Newsletters</p>

4. GAPPA-Based Content				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bimonthly posts or campaigns focusing on GAPPA’s information. • Showcase CityMove interventions aligning with GAPPA’s policy actions, demonstrating their effectiveness. <p>Objective: Educate and engage audiences about the connection between GAPPA and CityMove’s interventions, highlighting their global relevance.</p> <p>Impact: Strengthen understanding of GAPPA principles while positioning CityMove as a key contributor to achieving global physical activity goals.</p>	<p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn, Instagram, Blusky. • CityMove blog and newsletters. 	<p>Bimonthly posts and thematic campaigns throughout 2025:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • January 21 • April 10 • June 12 • October 9 		4 posts or campaigns focusing on GAPPA’s information.
5. April 2025 Campaign				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>April 6: International Day of Sport for Development and Peace – Showcase how CityMove fosters sustainable development through physical activity.</p> <p>April 7: World Health Day – Highlight the health impacts of interventions, linking them to WHO goals.</p> <p>Objective: Leverage international observances to amplify CityMove’s impact and reach new audiences.</p> <p>Impact: Increase awareness of CityMove’s contributions to global health and sustainable development.</p>	<p>Format: posts or campaign.</p> <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media platforms. • CityMove blog featuring intervention-specific success stories with data and quotes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Campaign planning in February–March; execution in April. 		1 campaign around two key dates (D-days) related to the project
6. Research Videos				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>Collaborate with junior researchers to create short, engaging video capsules focusing on the research carried out in each city and their interventions.</p> <p>Objective: Provide an engaging, accessible format to communicate</p>	<p>Format: Short videos (80-90 sec.) made by junior investigators</p> <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media platforms. 	<p>Publication in March 2025</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • March 		6 videos published

research findings and project progress. Impact: Foster understanding among diverse audiences while highlighting CityMove’s educational and research contributions.				
7. Call for and dissemination of Communities of Practice (CoP)				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
Summarise CoP discussions and outcomes in accessible formats (e.g., blogs, newsletters, social media posts). Highlight regional success stories and innovative practices through CityMove’s channels and EU platforms. Objective: To disseminate the insights, outcomes, and best practices from CoP discussions in an engaging and accessible manner, ensuring that knowledge and successful regional practices reach a wide audience. Impact: Extends the reach of CoP discussions to stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public, encouraging the adoption of successful interventions.	Channels: ● CityMove social media (LinkedIn, Instagram, and Twitter). ● CityMove blog and newsletters. ● EU platforms, including Horizon Results Platform and CORDIS.	● Q1 2025: Recruitment of CoP participants ● Q2 2025: Host initial CoP meetings in Europe, Latin America, and East Africa. ● Q3–Q4 2025: Quarterly CoP meetings, workshops, and knowledge-sharing activities.		1 campaign around CoP
8. Podcasts				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
Create six podcast episodes in 2025, covering themes such as GAPPA actions, intervention progress, and co-production. Themes: ● June: ● July: ● August: ● September: ● October: ● November:	Format: Podcast episodes lasting 10 to 12 minutes, in interview format, with audio inserts and two or three defined sections. All episodes will be part of Podcast Channels: ● Podcast platforms (Spreaker, or other)	Podcasts production: March to May 2025 Podcasts to launch in H2 2025. ● June 3 ● July 1 ● August 5 ● September 2 ● October 7 ● November 4		6 Podcasts produced and published

Objective: to provide an engaging and accessible format to share CityMove’s insights, research, and achievements with a diverse audience. Impact: Provides an interactive format that encourages listeners to connect with the project and its mission.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU platforms • CityMove website, and social media. 			
9. Use of EU Platforms				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>Publish articles, videos, and podcasts on CORDIS and Horizon Results Platform.</p> <p>For each of the communities of practice (CoP), produce an article, articulated with the results of the research, to be published on the European Union platforms.</p> <p>Objective: Strengthen alignment with Horizon EU initiatives and increase visibility among policymakers and researchers.</p> <p>Impact: Build CityMove’s reputation within the EU research community, driving awareness and collaboration.</p>	<p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU platforms • CityMove website, and social media. 	<p>Four times a year:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • July 10 to 14 • September 9 to 13 • November 8 to 12 • December 1 to 5 		<p>4 articles published on EU platforms (Cordis or Horizon EU)</p>
10. Articles for Targeted Media				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<p>Manage and update the project's media and journalist database city by city, ensuring they receive newsletters and key updates. Identify specialised media outlets to share CityMove’s research and secure at least two articles in targeted media.</p> <p>Objective: Raise awareness of CityMove’s research among specialised audiences, including policymakers, urban planners, health professionals, and researchers.</p> <p>Impact: Strengthen engagement with key stakeholders who can</p>		<p>May – November 2025</p>		<p>2 articles were placed in targeted media outlets.</p>

support and adopt CityMove's findings.				
11. Monitoring and Review				
Description, objective, and impact	Format and channels	Timeline		Indicators 2025
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct quarterly reviews of communication metrics (social media, newsletter performance, engagement rates). Compile a comprehensive 2025 Communication Impact Report by December. <p>Objective: Measure success and ensure accountability while refining strategies for 2026.</p>	<p>Document</p> <p>CityMove Tracking 2024-2025 document</p>	<p>Quarterly reviews; final report in December 2025.</p> <p>Quarterly reviews:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> April 4 July 4 October 3 December 27 <p>Final: December 29.</p>		<p>Updated M&E tracking doc.</p> <p>1 Final report.</p>

Internal project communication:

With the support of the general coordination of the project:

- Hold monthly CCC project meetings to review the main communication tasks for each city and upcoming activities.
- Hold monthly touchpoint meetings with each city.

Communication with media and journalists:

In coordination with the partners in each city,

- Update the project's database of media and journalist contacts, city by city.
- Ensure that the project newsletters are forwarded to the database of media and journalists in each city, along with contact details for further information.
- Identify a media outlet in each city specialising in health, physical activity or urban planning, to send periodic updates on the project and the results of its research.

Cross-cutting recommendations

- It is recommended to consolidate a database of project photographs. These platforms allow different users (for example, focal points of communication by country) to upload their images in albums that can be organized by country, year, and activity.

Additional content that can be shared or adapted for social media:

- Publish the images and content created for the City-Move website clearly and shortly.
- Share information from third parties, such as the United Nations, other universities, national and international organisations, and institutions that address the project's themes (e.g., reports on physical activity).
- Join in with simple messages on D-Days related to the central themes of City-Move.

- Replicate content from partners in which they present or mention the project.
- Replicate press releases and academic articles on the central themes of the project.
- From time to time, generate a survey or question in the community about general topics, such as how much physical activity they do or whether they know a key concept.
- Identify and replicate information published by the European Union on issues relevant to the project.

Work schedule

Schedule of communication programming 2025 activities:

The DEC project schedule, along with the annual schedules for each DEC programming, are [available in this document](#): CITY-MOVE DEC Strategy . Here is a general picture: [Available in this document](#):

 SM Calendar

A calendar of 2025 publications on social networks has also been created. [Available in this document](#): Social Media January-June 2025

